

“DETERMINING THE CONTAMINATION AND MOISTURE CONTENT OF COTTON BASED ON INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES, AND MONITORING THE QUALITY OF COTTON STORED IN WAREHOUSES.”

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Abstract: In this article, to provide more information about the process of raw cotton processing, the effect of using innovative methods, to determine the degree of contamination and moisture of this received cotton, so that they have complete information about this science. The procedure used in the inspection is the law and regulations. Helping them to acquire theoretical knowledge, practical skills and high qualifications from the module "The role and importance of preparation points in the storage of raw cotton and the process of quality control during storage".

Key words: Cotton dirt and moisture interactive method, innovative technology, Preparation point, LKM device, P-2 light polarizing device, desiccator, "Uzdavstandart".

Before analyzing cotton for contamination and moisture content, a sample of 400–500 g is taken from each large container into a smaller container and stored for 24 hours for moisture control testing. The 24-hour storage period is counted from the moment the controlled portion of the sample is placed into a small container (for moisture determination) and into a larger container (for contamination determination).

After conducting daily analyses of moisture and contamination, the remaining part of the sample is retained for control testing of quality and contamination and is stored in paper bags.

The small sample container is labeled, and a tag indicating the date, farm, brigade, selection and industrial varieties, and the batch group is attached. After 24 hours, the control samples are added to the corresponding batches.

For the received cotton, innovative technologies are used, and sampling and analyses to determine its grade, moisture content, and contamination level are carried out in accordance with national standards No. 643-95, 592-92, 593-92, and 644-95 (1, 2, 3, 4). These analyses are performed using standard samples or instruments that have been certified by the metrological service of “O'zDavStandart.”

Sampling procedures, the work of laboratory personnel, and the condition of laboratory equipment are supervised by the head of the Technical Control Department (TCD) of the cotton processing plant.

The laboratory of the procurement point must be equipped with the following instruments: an O'z-7M drying oven; USX-1 and VXS or VXS-M1 moisture meters; an LKM device for determining cotton contamination; an LPS-4 instrument for determining fiber grade; a PPV gin fiber cleaner; an SXL-3 laboratory dryer for cotton; technical balances with small weights; a microscope; a P-2 polarized light attachment for the microscope; a desiccator; and containers (large and small) for sampling.

The permissible differences in control measurements using the LPS-4 instrument should not exceed 2.5% for cotton fiber. If the differences between the results exceed the allowable limit,

two additional samples are measured using the LPS-4, and the average value is calculated based on the measurement results.

The difference between the results of two sample analyses in contamination control tests should not exceed 0.6% (absolute) when the contamination level is up to 10%, and should not exceed 1.0% (absolute) when the contamination level is above 10%.

In control analyses, the difference between the results of two samples for cotton moisture content should not exceed 0.5% when the moisture content is up to 10.0%, and should not exceed 5.0% (relative) when the moisture content is above 10%.

If the differences between the initial and control analysis results do not exceed the limits specified above, the initial analysis is considered valid.

Daily laboratory analyses are conducted to verify the correctness of sampling and to determine the grade, contamination level, and moisture content of cotton accepted by classifiers and the laboratory. For this purpose, on the day following acceptance, composite cotton samples are taken from each batch collected at the procurement point from the cotton received on a single day, with the participation of a classifier.

A label indicating the cotton's selection and industrial varieties, harvesting type, and the number of the batch or stack from which the sample was taken is attached to each sample. After that, the moisture content, contamination level, and grade of cotton are determined in the laboratory using appropriate instruments.

The results of the analysis are mandatory for the classifier. Based on these results, the classifier must take measures to ensure proper acceptance and grouping of cotton.

The contamination and moisture indicators according to batch formation data must correspond to the data recorded during acceptance or may have deviations within the allowable limits specified above.

In order to assess the quality of cotton received at the procurement point, a composite sample is prepared for each formed cotton batch in accordance with the national standard "Cotton. Sampling Methods".

Quality control of cotton received at the procurement point plays an important role during cotton acceptance. Its accuracy determines not only the income of the cotton plant but also the proper formation of cotton stacks, ensuring reliable storage of cotton. Sampling is considered the initial and most responsible stage of cotton quality control. At the cotton procurement point, sampling is carried out in accordance with the national standard 643-95 "Cotton. Sampling Methods" (1). Sampling is also permitted at cotton unloading sites.

For sampling purposes, a permanently covered shelter is usually equipped, where a location is selected to protect sample containers used for determining cotton moisture and contamination from sunlight, dust, and precipitation. To determine cotton quality indicators, a composite sample is formed from samples taken from random points in different parts of the delivered cotton batch. Interactive methods are also used.

A "batch" is understood as a quantity of cotton of uniform quality belonging to a single selection-industrial variety, documented under a single transport consignment note.

From each delivered batch, the classifier at the procurement point selects samples manually from different points in the presence of the cotton supplier before the cotton is weighed. Sampling from different points is also permitted at the unloading sites where cotton is delivered.

From each 2 tons of the delivered cotton batch, samples weighing 100–150 g are taken from at least three different points at various depths. The contamination and moisture content of cotton are determined in the procurement point laboratory based on samples within the formed batches, calculated as an average daily value for each farm (department or brigade). The average daily sample consists of a collection of samples taken from cotton delivered within one day. It is prepared as follows.

Cotton samples taken from different points are placed into a tightly sealed small container (1 kg capacity) for testing moisture and contamination using instruments. The label of the container indicates the consignment note number of the delivering farm, batch number, harvesting type, and cotton grade.

Then, the samples collected in small containers are placed into larger containers with a capacity of 6–8 kg (approximate dimensions: height 0.7 m, diameter 0.4 m). A label is attached to the large container indicating the farm, department, brigades, selection and industrial cotton grade, harvesting type, and batch number.

Large containers should be stored in a special designated place in the laboratory or department, away from heating devices. A composite daily sample with a capacity of at least 3–4 kg is collected throughout the entire day of acceptance, and once a day it is subjected to laboratory analysis of moisture and contamination in accordance with standard 3–136.

Conclusion

The application of modern approaches to determining the moisture content and contamination of received cotton creates opportunities to develop interest in scientific research, analyze the current conditions and situation of the industry in different regions, introduce new systems, and form both theoretical and practical knowledge.

In the teaching process, the use of “new modern pedagogical technologies” produces good results. The main issue is reflected in the level of provision with literature, manuals, methodological guidelines, handouts, and modern information-technical tools, as well as the ability to effectively deliver them to students. In this regard, first of all, the instructor must have the necessary skills to work with such materials.

This problem can, to some extent, be solved through the modules developed by the instructor for this course. Before studying the theoretical and practical topics of the subject “Drying of Cotton Raw Material,” students first acquire knowledge about the importance of the cotton drying industry. In particular, they gain practical skills in improving cotton cultivation technologies.

Based on the above, the effective use of these opportunities depends on the teacher’s pedagogical skills. In this process, the teacher must be creative and possess deep, comprehensive knowledge. It is also necessary for the teacher to widely use interactive teaching methods in lessons and to develop students’ logical thinking skills.

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